

POLICY BRIEF

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BRAZIL AND DEFENSE COOPERATION: A BRIEF ANALYSIS FOR A STRATEGIC POLICY

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POLICY STATEMENT

Political arrangements and established regimes depend on cooperation mechanisms to maintain stability in between countries. Thus, like other countries, Brazil maintained its foreign relations based on a cooperative perspective, collective gains, and peaceful and institutional value. However, since the current government, Brazil did not promote our cooperative and multilateral frameworks, especially in its relations with neighboring countries based on the South-South cooperation instrument. In this sense, it is urgent to think about new directions regarding cooperation relations with countries in the southern axis or the Global South. Therefore, as a priority, we will consider for this analysis the defense cooperation relations, the strategic frameworks for establishing trust, the exchanges based on technical cooperation, and bottom-up relations through institutions and agencies that continue to move this forward.

This policy brief analyzes the defense cooperation policies in the Brazilian strategic environment, fostered by its technical cooperation within South America, Africa, and the Portuguese Language Community. This relationship of deepening defense technical cooperation had the participation of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the Ministry of Defense, and other stakeholders involved in the expansion of the Brazilian defense sector, in the benefit of international reputation, and conditions that may reduce Brazil's vulnerabilities in the 21st Century.

BACKGROUND

The international cooperation process for Brazil has always been part of its foreign policy. As an element of international confidence, Brazil launched itself into the world as a global player through its peaceful relations, inclusive diplomacy. It effectively participated in peace missions such as MINUSTAH and UNIFIL, two prominent participations alongside the United Nations, that made the country gain repercussion and voice in international forums, and of course, plead for a seat on the most critical decision council of the UN.

Throughout this confidence-building process, Brazil had invested in the regional integration process by consolidating the Southern Common Market, MERCOSUR, in 1991, with the signing of the Treaty of Asunción, which provided a model of integration and cooperation among countries such as Brazil, Argentina, Paraguay, and Uruguay. Mercosur had become the model for the stability of relations in the region and had sought, through the deepening of its regulations, an ever-greater approximation in trade policies, in the peaceful resolution of disputes, in the consolidation of democracy, and the economic autonomy of the southern region of America.

Cooperation through Mercosur became markedly technical, deepened with exchanges in education, in the regulations that initiated the bloc's citizenship procedures, in legal mechanisms for resolving disputes such as the Permanent Review Court. However, the bloc stagnated its trade mechanisms, impeded bilateral ties, did not expand business with the diversification of products in its internal trade, and paralyzed its integration governance.

In this way, Brazil sought to expand its relations beyond the South Atlantic, kept its west axis stable with a good relationship with its neighbors, and headed east to gain support and closer ties with the coastal Atlantic countries and the Community of Countries of Portuguese Language. This new cooperation process made it possible to advance in the defense sector and in what we know as defense cooperation and defense diplomacy. In this sphere, we have advanced cooperation models such as in training, capacity building, defense products, and defense institutions of partner countries. Thus, Brazil has fostered a safer geopolitical and geostrategic space, known in the literature as the Brazilian Strategic Environment.

With the deepening of the relations in the defense area, Brazil created a model of governance in regional defense and, in 2008, together with the countries of South America, it implemented the Union of South American Nations, being a model of regional integration with more countries involved, all from South America except for French Guiana, and standardized with partners a series of strategic areas for regional development, including the area of defense, establishing the South American Defense Council.

The South American Defense Council had as its main proposal the joint elaboration of defense policies, the exchange between civilian and military of the armed forces of the member countries, the integration of industrial bases, which would, in principle, be favorable for the growth of Brazil's defense industrial base, coordinated mutual aid policies, training, and capacity building of force agents, integrated cooperation, information sharing, and various activities that expanded and deepened cooperation.

FINDINGS

By analyzing the role of the South American Defense Council, we realized that the attempt at Defense Governance would gain a great deal of space in the region if the adopted policies reached common goals-against common transnational threats that plague us in the border region, including drug trafficking which is more widespread within the states, expanding business, logistics and domain region, human trafficking, animal trafficking, among others. Coordinated security and defense policies could become an interagency model that would go beyond national borders to communicate, know their organizational culture models, their models of operational action against common threats.

However, political divergences maximized losses and strategic partnerships such as the UNASUR model or the South American Defense Council. The states themselves emptied the institution, no longer betting on this partnership. With the change of governments and ideological exchanges, the model was replaced by PROSUL – a program for the Progress and Integration of South America, which has not yet had any relevant development in terms of regional integration.

When analyzing international cooperation theories or even game theory, we observe the low rationality of regional actors in the elements of loss with the consequent emptying of cooperation relations a greater competitive space based on the ideological element and not necessarily the commercial element or any other sphere leads to conflict. The impasses in the ideological sphere caused South America to lose itself in its deeper regional integration project and the newest governance models in strategic areas such as defense.

Even so, the relations of continuity of cooperation relations went beyond institutional conflicts and remained in a bottom-up manner, that is, the strengthening of relations between Brazil and its partner neighbors continues to be closer and firmer because the elements known as "end of the line" or executors of the actions, provided voluntary and necessary continuity of cooperation, and thus remained in the field of defense.

Since 1994, Brazil began its financing and aid programs for cooperation in defense with countries on the African coast such as Namibia, later with Costa Verde, South Africa, Mozambique, Guinea-Bissau. The programs were aimed at military training, defense agreements, arms sales, creation of navy outposts, military training, and exchange with our armed forces.

Over time, we gained international space and respect, especially in our strategic environment, participating in various forums and discussing our experiences. However, Brazil had abandoned its multilateral relations priority. In recent years, the ideological struggle has surpassed Brazil's strategic thinking of expansion and leadership, giving little voice to Brazil, which had previously reached huge dimensions in the international sphere. Its projects are institutionally paralyzed, gaining efforts in individual relationships and by executing agencies through the bottom-up manner. This model is always present in the continuity and enhancement of cooperation.

CONCLUSIONS

Finally, we can consider that the defense cooperation process is an important mechanism for mutual assistance in constructing common policies in defense and the structuring of strategic defense governance mechanisms. Advances in capacity building, training, and institutions that carry out joint activities are again in trust between countries, strengthening partnerships, and implementing new projects that need to gain momentum to help reduce sensitivities and vulnerabilities of the impacts of interdependence in today's world.

It is necessary to appreciate that the path to a safe and stable region lies with the arrangements created in between neighboring countries, which can geopolitically visualize their role in the world and use the tools of negotiation and cooperation to deepen their relations. In this sense, governance models based on integration such as former UNASUR need to face the dilemmas of governmental differences and become solid forums with a high reputation, which maintain continuity in their processes and establish institutionalized structures, with clear procedures and regulations as to deepen cooperation.

SUGGESTIONS

Some suggestions are important for cooperation policies in the field of defense for Brazil. Thus, here are reflections to be discussed by cooperative theorists, or even specialists and academics in defense studies:

1- Brazil needs to resume its leadership role in the surrounding strategic region, whether bringing its partners closer to South American countries, with blocs such as Mercosur, or with countries with greater cultural and linguistic proximity such as CPLP, or even in a geostrategic way with those bordering the South Atlantic.

- 2- Consolidating governance models in the defense area, or deepening defense policies through institutionalized cooperation or regional integration, is important to safeguard countries from common threats and get to know neighbors and partnerships through peaceful relations.
- 3- These "forums" where common defense models and policies are debated and structured are essential for deepening relations of trust, bringing Brazil back to the world stage as a global player.
- 4- Partnerships are cooperation networks that foster exchange, training, and common thinking in defense. Furthermore, they can be vectors of a defense economy policy that favors Brazil and its defense industrial base.
- 5- Policies must maintain continuity and discipline in maintaining dialogue and negotiation even if there are differences in between partners. Cooperation should be rationalized and pragmatic, as to meet the collective perspectives, leaving aside the competitive and individualized aspects that often impact domestic politics.
- 6- The challenges of domestic policies and political-ideological clashes cannot confuse the process of cooperation in defense, which is medium and long-term policies, requiring continuity in the process.

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